

1 **Control of Muc5b and Muc16 by HPV E6.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described
7 functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We
8 demonstrate here control of mucins Muc5b and Muc16 by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV
9 E6 across type: for both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

10 Citations

11 1. Roy, M.G., Livraghi-Butrico, A., Fletcher, A.A., McElwee, M.M., Evans, S.E., Boerner, R.M.,
12 Alexander, S.N., Bellinghausen, L.K., Song, A.S., Petrova, Y.M. and Tuvim, M.J., 2014. Muc5b is required
13 for airway defence. *Nature*, 505(7483), pp.412-416.

14 GSE228187
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28